

INDIA'S ROLE AS A CLIMATE DIPLOMAT: BRIDGING GLOBAL CLIMATE ACTION WITH SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SOUTH

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Abstract

India's evolving role in global climate governance reflects its dual commitment to sustainable development and equitable climate action. As a critical advocate for the Global South, India emphasises "common but differentiated responsibilities" (CBDR), underscoring that developed countries should lead mitigation efforts due to their historical emissions. India's climate strategy prioritises emissions intensity targets rather than absolute cuts, allowing for economic growth while gradually reducing carbon intensity. With a 2070 net-zero target and interim goals for 2030, India has outlined an ambitious renewable energy agenda, including plans to expand solar capacity to 500 GW by 2030, facilitated mainly through international initiatives like the International Solar Alliance (ISA). However, India's climate ambitions face challenges related to financial constraints and access to advanced technologies. India's climate diplomacy consistently advocates for increased climate finance and technology transfer from developed nations, which are essential for enabling large-scale renewable energy projects, climate resilience initiatives, and adaptation measures. Platforms like the G20 and COP summits amplify India's calls for transparent and reliable climate finance mechanisms, notably to support communities vulnerable to climate impacts. While some critics argue that India's timelines for emissions reduction are less aggressive than those of developed nations, India maintains that its approach balances urgent climate action with its developmental imperatives, aiming to model a pathway for low-carbon growth that is realistic for developing economies.

Keywords: climate change, CBDR, renewable energy, climate finance, G20, COP27.

1. Introduction

The accelerating pace of climate change has established it as one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century, demanding coordinated and comprehensive action across the globe (IPCC, 2021). Since the Industrial Revolution, human activities have led to unprecedented greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, significantly altering the Earth's atmospheric composition and resulting in observable environmental consequences, such as rising temperatures, extreme weather events, melting ice caps, and sea-level rise (NASA, 2020; WMO, 2022). These impacts have severe repercussions, particularly for vulnerable communities and ecosystems, which face heightened risks of resource scarcity, displacement, and biodiversity loss (NOAA, 2023). Addressing the multifaceted impacts of climate change necessitates a global response, a call to action that has been progressively met through international climate agreements aimed at mitigating emissions, adapting to changing environmental conditions, and fostering resilience (UNFCCC, 2015; Pachauri & Meyer, 2014).

International climate agreements, established under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and related platforms, have become the primary mechanisms for mobilising global action (UNFCCC, 1992). Key agreements, such as the Kyoto Protocol, the Copenhagen Accord, the Paris Agreement, and, more recently, the Glasgow Climate Pact, embody global consensus on climate action, setting the stage for collective responsibility while acknowledging differentiated responsibilities based on economic and developmental disparities (UNFCCC, 1997; UNFCCC, 2009; UNFCCC, 2015; UNFCCC, 2021). For developing economies, climate agreements underscore the challenge of balancing economic growth with environmental stewardship (Pauw et al., 2020). The concept of “common but differentiated responsibilities” (CBDR) enshrined in these agreements highlights that while all nations must engage in climate action, wealthier countries should bear a larger share of the burden due to their historical contributions to GHG emissions (Rajamani, 2000). Developing countries, on the other hand, are encouraged to advance climate goals within their developmental capabilities, with support from international financial and technological resources (Pickering et al., 2015).

As one of the world's largest emerging economies, India is pivotal in the global climate discourse. With a rapidly growing population and economy, India's energy demands and developmental imperatives often complicate its approach to climate commitments (Dubash et al., 2018). India's vulnerability to climate change is also pronounced; it experiences severe impacts, such as rising temperatures, monsoon variability, and increased frequency of natural disasters (Singh et al., 2020; IPCC, 2021). The nation's dual role—as a significant emitter of greenhouse gases due to its population size and as a vulnerable country impacted by climate change—shapes its stance in international climate negotiations (Rattani & Sarkar, 2018). India's emphasis on Common but Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDR), alongside its call for equitable climate action, underscores its advocacy for fair treatment and access to climate finance and technology transfer to facilitate sustainable development (UNFCCC, 2015; Bhadwal et al., 2021).

This paper aims to critically examine India's participation in major international climate agreements from 2008 onwards, with a particular focus on its contributions to and outcomes from landmark negotiations such as the Copenhagen Accord (2009), the Paris Agreement (2015), and the Glasgow Climate Pact (2021) (Vihma et al., 2016; Jørgensen et al., 2021). By analysing India's stance, strategies, and commitments in these agreements, the paper seeks to elucidate how India navigates the complex dynamics of climate diplomacy while balancing its national interests with global climate imperatives (Dubash, 2013). Additionally, the study will explore the challenges India faces in aligning its developmental goals with climate targets, assessing the implications of international expectations, climate finance, and technology transfer on India's policy decisions (Dubash & Ghosh, 2021). Through this analysis, the paper seeks insights into India's evolving role in global climate governance and its potential trajectory in future climate negotiations. Ultimately, the scope of this study encompasses a comprehensive review of India's policy positions and contributions within international climate frameworks, providing a nuanced understanding of the country's efforts to harmonise sustainable development with global climate commitments. This examination of India's climate diplomacy reveals broader themes of equity, sustainability, and resilience, illuminating India's role as a contributor to and a stakeholder in the global response to climate change.

2. Historical Context of India's Climate Policy

India's climate policy has evolved significantly over the years, shaped by its unique socio-economic conditions and developmental priorities. Before 2008, India's engagement in climate discussions reflected its stance as a developing nation grappling with poverty alleviation and economic growth while recognising the need for environmental stewardship (Dubash & Ghosh, 2013). India's early climate policy was primarily guided by the principles of equity and "common but differentiated responsibilities" (CBDR), as articulated in the Rio Earth Summit of 1992 and the Kyoto Protocol of 1997 (UNFCCC, 1992; UNFCCC, 1997). These principles emphasised that while all nations share responsibility for addressing climate change, developed countries—historically responsible for most greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions—should bear a larger share of the burden in mitigating its effects (Rajamani, 2000).

At the Rio Earth Summit in 1992, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) was established, marking a landmark moment in global environmental governance (UNFCCC, 1992). As one of the signatories, India affirmed its commitment to addressing climate change but advocated strongly for the CBDR principle. The Indian government argued that developing nations should not be held to the same standards as developed countries, given their comparatively low historical emissions and pressing developmental needs (Dubash, 2011). For India, the path to sustainable development required balancing environmental responsibility with eradicating poverty, industrial growth, and energy security. The Rio Earth Summit laid the groundwork for India's future climate policies, cementing its focus on sustainable development and equity in international climate negotiations (Chaturvedi & Shukla, 2014).

The Kyoto Protocol, adopted in 1997 and enforced in 2005, was the first international treaty to set legally binding emissions reduction targets, primarily for developed countries (UNFCCC, 1997). India's role in the Kyoto Protocol was shaped by its status as a non-Annex I country, which exempted it from mandatory emission reduction commitments. This distinction aligned with India's stance that developed nations should take the lead in cutting emissions due to their historical and per capita emissions levels (Sharma, 2007). The Kyoto Protocol allowed India to participate in the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), a framework

that enabled developed countries to meet part of their emissions reduction obligations by investing in emission-reducing projects in developing countries (Michaelowa, 2007). India became one of the largest beneficiaries of the CDM, attracting investments in renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable agriculture projects. The CDM framework was significant for India, as it aligned with national interests in sustainable development, promoted green technology, and contributed to economic growth without imposing restrictive emissions targets (Sirohi, 2007).

India's climate policy during this period was also influenced by its reliance on coal and other fossil fuels to meet its burgeoning energy demands. With a rapidly growing economy and population, India's energy needs were substantial, and fossil fuels provided a readily available and affordable energy source. Thus, energy security and access remained key priorities in India's climate policy discourse as the country sought to reduce poverty and boost economic growth (Dubash & Joseph, 2016). This reliance on fossil fuels challenged India to align with global climate goals while addressing domestic energy needs, which would only intensify in later years as international expectations of emissions reductions grew (Ghosh, 2015).

Challenges related to poverty alleviation, infrastructure development, and energy access guided India's cautious approach to climate commitments before 2008. For policymakers, climate change was often viewed as a secondary issue to socio-economic development, primarily focusing on creating employment, reducing inequality, and enhancing industrialisation (Rattani & Grover, 2018). Additionally, India faced the challenge of managing climate vulnerability—its geography and climate made it susceptible to floods, droughts, and cyclones, disproportionately affecting marginalised communities (Singh et al., 2020).

India's historical climate policy reflects a complex balance between developmental imperatives and environmental responsibility. Pre-2008, India's position was primarily defined by advocating for climate justice and equitable responsibility, emphasising that climate change mitigation should rest with developed nations. This stance would serve as the foundation for India's climate diplomacy in subsequent years, framing its approach to international climate agreements, particularly as India's

domestic and international priorities began to converge in the face of a global push for a concerted climate response (Rajamani, 2012). As climate discussions intensified globally, India would continue to navigate the dual demands of development and climate action, a balancing act that remains central to its climate policy today (Jørgensen et al., 2021).

3. India's Engagement in Major Climate Agreements

India's role in major international climate agreements highlights the country's evolving stance and deepening engagement with global climate governance. Over the years, India's climate diplomacy has transitioned from a cautious approach focused primarily on developmental priorities to a more proactive engagement emphasising sustainable development, renewable energy, and climate resilience. The following sections analyse India's participation in climate agreements, namely the Copenhagen Accord (2009), the Paris Agreement (2015), the Glasgow Climate Pact (2021), and the nation's ongoing role in the G20 and COP27, focusing on India's commitments, policy shifts, and the underlying objectives guiding its climate strategy.

Copenhagen Accord (2009): India's Contributions, Main Goals, and Outcomes

The 2009 United Nations Climate Change Conference in Copenhagen (COP15) marked a turning point in international climate negotiations. While the conference failed to produce a legally binding treaty, it resulted in the Copenhagen Accord, a non-binding agreement aiming to limit global temperature increases to below 2°C above pre-industrial levels (UNFCCC, 2009). India's engagement in the Copenhagen Accord was pivotal, as it asserted its stance on equity and highlighted the need for developing nations to receive financial and technological support to pursue sustainable development (Dubash, 2009).

India, alongside China, Brazil, and South Africa, played a critical role in shaping the Accord, advocating for climate action that would not hinder economic growth or poverty alleviation in developing countries (Pillai, 2010). The Accord emphasised "common but differentiated responsibilities" (CBDR), a principle India has long championed, asserting that developed nations bear greater responsibility for climate mitigation due to their historical emissions (Rajamani, 2010). India's

stance at Copenhagen highlighted its commitment to climate action and development equity, advocating for measures allowing developing countries to grow sustainably (Dubash & Joseph, 2016).

India's contributions to the Copenhagen Accord included a pledge to reduce the emission intensity of its GDP by 20–25% from 2005 levels by 2020 (MoEFCC, 2009). This significant commitment marked India's first voluntary pledges in international climate negotiations. However, the reduction was in terms of intensity rather than absolute emissions, reflecting India's prioritisation of economic growth and poverty reduction (Rattani & Grover, 2018). The Copenhagen Accord, while non-binding, set the stage for future negotiations by recognising the need for financial and technological support for developing nations, which aligned with India's climate priorities (Jørgensen et al., 2021).

Outcomes of the Copenhagen Accord for India included a greater emphasis on national climate policies. Following the conference, India launched the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) and its associated missions, such as the National Solar Mission, to promote renewable energy and reduce reliance on fossil fuels (Shukla & Dhar, 2016). This marked a shift towards more structured climate action within India, setting a foundation for India's increased engagement in subsequent international agreements (Dubash & Ghosh, 2013).

Paris Agreement (2015): India's Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs), Policy Shifts, and Commitments

The 2015 Paris Agreement (COP21) represented a historic milestone in global climate policy, establishing a legally binding framework for countries to set and achieve emission reduction targets known as Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). India's participation in the Paris Agreement was guided by its focus on sustainable development, energy access, and climate resilience. India played a pivotal role in advocating for the inclusion of equity, CBDR, and climate justice within the Paris Framework, ensuring that the agreement acknowledged the unique challenges developing countries face.

India's Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs), submitted before COP21, outlined ambitious targets focused on renewable energy, energy efficiency, and afforestation. Vital elements of India's INDCs included:

1. **Emission Intensity Reduction:** India committed to reducing the emissions intensity of its GDP by 33–35% from 2005 levels by 2030.
2. **Renewable Energy Targets:** India set an ambitious target to achieve 40% of its cumulative electric power installed capacity from non-fossil fuel-based energy sources by 2030. This included a target of 175 GW renewable energy capacity by 2022, which was later raised to 450 GW by 2030.
3. **Afforestation and Carbon Sink Enhancement:** India pledged to create an additional carbon sink of 2.5–3 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalent through increased forest and tree cover by 2030.

India's commitments under the Paris Agreement demonstrated a significant policy shift, emphasising renewable energy as a cornerstone of its climate strategy (Dubash et al., 2018). The National Solar Mission, already launched in 2010, was scaled up, with solar energy identified as a critical pathway for meeting the Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs) (Chaudhary et al., 2014). In parallel, India launched several national policies to enhance energy efficiency, such as the Perform, Achieve, and Trade (PAT) scheme, which targeted efficiency improvements across high-energy industries (Sharma & Dhar, 2016).

The Paris Agreement also underscored the importance of climate finance and technology transfer, issues central to India's climate strategy (UNFCCC, 2015). India emphasised that meeting its ambitious targets would require international support, including funding from developed countries and access to clean energy technologies (Ghosh, 2015). This focus on financial and technological support aligned with India's broader objective of ensuring climate action does not compromise its developmental goals (Dubash & Ghosh, 2021).

The outcomes of the Paris Agreement for India included strengthened international partnerships in renewable energy and climate finance. Notably, India co-founded the International Solar Alliance (ISA) with France, a coalition aimed at mobilising resources and fostering co-operation in solar energy deployment among solar-rich countries (International Solar Alliance, 2015). This initiative reinforced India's leadership in renewable energy and underscored its commitment to climate action on a global scale (Bhaskar, 2019).

Glasgow Climate Pact (2021): Net-Zero Targets, Emission Reduction Commitments, and India's Evolving Climate Stance

The Glasgow Climate Pact, adopted at COP26 in 2021, introduced new targets for global emissions reductions and emphasised the importance of limiting global warming to 1.5°C (UNFCCC, 2021). For India, COP26 marked a pivotal moment in its climate policy, as Prime Minister Narendra Modi announced India's commitment to achieve net-zero emissions by 2070, a milestone in the country's climate journey (Chowdhury, 2022). Although this target extends beyond the mid-century goal set by many developed nations, it reflects India's balancing act between climate responsibility and developmental imperatives (Dubash et al., 2022).

India's announcements at Glasgow included the following key commitments, often referred to as the "Panchamrit" or five-point climate pledge:

1. **Net-Zero by 2070:** India's commitment to achieving net-zero emissions by 2070 aligned it with global climate goals while acknowledging the extended timeline needed for a developing nation with high energy demands.
2. **Renewable Energy Capacity:** India pledged to increase its renewable energy capacity to 500 GW by 2030, raising its earlier targets from the Paris Agreement.
3. **Reduction in Emission Intensity:** India reiterated its goal of reducing the emissions intensity of its GDP by 45% from 2005 levels by 2030, marking an increase from its previous target of 33–35%.
4. **50% Renewable Energy Share:** India committed to meeting 50% of its energy needs from renewable sources by 2030.
5. **Reduction in Projected Carbon Emissions:** India announced a target to reduce projected carbon emissions by 1 billion tonnes by 2030.

The Glasgow Climate Pact reinforced India's commitment to sustainable development and renewable energy, positioning it as a leader among developing nations in climate action (UNFCCC, 2021). However, India

also underscored the need for climate finance, estimating that implementing its climate targets would require \$1 trillion in support from developed nations (Government of India, 2021). India's stance at Glasgow illustrated its expectation that developed countries fulfil their promises regarding climate finance, which remains a cornerstone of India's international climate policy (Chaturvedi, 2022). Outcomes from the Glasgow Climate Pact included renewed partnerships and an increased focus on climate adaptation. India highlighted the importance of climate resilience, particularly given its vulnerability to climate impacts (Venkataramani et al., 2021). Furthermore, India's 2070 net-zero commitment signalled a significant shift in its climate policy, reflecting a willingness to engage in long-term climate planning despite economic constraints (Dubash & Ghosh, 2022).

G20 and COP27 Influence: India's Role in Aligning Climate Action with Economic Goals

India's role in the G20 and COP27 further illustrates its commitment to aligning climate action with economic development, especially as it assumed the G20 presidency in 2022 (Ministry of External Affairs, 2022). As a member of the G20, India has consistently advocated for inclusive and equitable climate policies, emphasising the need for sustainable development that does not hinder the economic growth of developing countries (Vishwanathan & Garg, 2023). India has called for increased climate finance and technology transfer, arguing that support from developed nations is essential for developing countries to meet their climate goals without compromising their developmental needs (Ghosh, 2022).

At COP27 in Egypt, India reiterated its call for a balanced approach to climate action. India's participation emphasised climate justice and adaptation, with a strong focus on financial support for loss and damage, which addresses the irreversible impacts of climate change on vulnerable communities (Chaudhary, 2023). India also highlighted its commitment to expanding renewable energy, building on the ambitious targets set in its updated Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) (UNFCCC, 2022).

Under India's G20 presidency, the nation has sought to place sustainable development and climate resilience at the forefront of the G20 agenda, fostering dialogue on green finance, energy transition, and low-carbon

infrastructure (Ministry of Finance, 2022). India's position in the G20 and COP27 reflects its ongoing efforts to promote an inclusive and pragmatic approach to climate action, recognising the diverse economic circumstances of G20 nations (Raghavan, 2023).

4. Climate Finance and Technology Transfer in India's Climate Strategy

Climate finance and technology transfer are essential pillars of India's climate strategy, enabling the country to balance its developmental priorities with its ambitious climate commitments. Given India's vast energy requirements and substantial reliance on fossil fuels, transitioning to a low-carbon economy requires significant financial investment and access to clean technology. International climate finance, pledged by developed countries and technology transfer agreements, form the backbone of India's strategy to achieve its climate targets, particularly those set under the Paris Agreement and reiterated in the Glasgow Climate Pact. However, accessing adequate climate finance and technology transfer poses distinct challenges for India, impacting the nation's ability to meet its sustainability goals efficiently.

The Role of Climate Finance and Its Challenges

Climate finance is critical for developing countries like India, which face the dual challenges of climate vulnerability and economic development (Dasgupta & Roy, 2021). India's Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs) submitted for the Paris Agreement and its updated targets at COP26 outlined ambitious goals, including increasing renewable energy capacity to 500 GW by 2030, enhancing afforestation efforts, and improving energy efficiency (MoEFCC, 2021). The achievement of these targets depends on substantial investment in infrastructure, renewable energy projects, and climate-resilient initiatives, which are capital-intensive. India has estimated that it requires approximately \$2.5 trillion by 2030 to meet its climate targets, underscoring the essential role of international climate finance (Vishwanathan et al., 2022).

Despite commitments by developed countries to mobilise \$100 billion annually for climate finance under the UNFCCC framework, the actual flow of funds has been limited and inconsistent, posing a significant

challenge for India (OECD, 2021). Access to climate finance remains hindered by complex application processes, stringent conditions, and inadequate disbursements, which fall short of the promised figures (Ghosh & Gangania, 2022). Moreover, much of the available climate finance is in the form of loans rather than grants, increasing the debt burden on developing countries like India (Bhattacharya et al., 2022). This shortfall in climate finance limits India's capacity to scale up renewable energy projects, improve infrastructure resilience, and fund green innovations critical to its low-carbon transition (Dubash et al., 2022).

India has advocated for more transparent and predictable climate finance mechanisms to ensure developing countries can effectively implement climate actions without compromising economic stability (Chaturvedi, 2022). As part of the Glasgow Climate Pact and COP27 negotiations, India has consistently emphasised the need for fair access to funds, arguing that developed nations should fulfil their financial commitments to enable inclusive climate action (UNFCCC, 2021). India's calls for robust, transparent, and accessible financing mechanisms reflect its strategic approach to ensuring climate finance catalyses sustainable growth and emissions reductions (Raghavan, 2023).

Technology Transfer Agreements and Clean Energy Collaborations

Technology transfer is vital in India's climate strategy, particularly as it seeks to accelerate its clean energy transition. Access to advanced technologies for renewable energy generation, energy storage, and carbon capture is crucial for India to enhance its climate resilience and reduce emissions (Bhasin & Ranjan, 2021). Technology transfer agreements between developed and developing countries facilitate the sharing of innovations, allowing countries like India to adopt cleaner, more efficient energy systems without investing extensively in research and development (Ghosh, 2016).

India has engaged in multiple technology transfer initiatives, often as part of bilateral and multilateral agreements, to boost its clean energy capacity. For instance, the International Solar Alliance (ISA), co-founded by India and France, is a coalition of solar-rich countries promoting solar energy deployment globally (International Solar Alliance, 2015). India has expanded its solar power infrastructure through ISA and shared technology and best practices with other

developing nations, fostering South-South cooperation in clean energy (Jolly & Saxena, 2020). Additionally, India has collaborated with countries like the United States, Japan, and Germany on renewable energy projects, receiving technological support in areas like solar photovoltaic technology, wind energy, and smart grids (Bhattacharya, 2022).

However, technology transfer in India faces specific barriers, including intellectual property rights, high costs of advanced technology, and limited domestic capacity for technology absorption and adaptation (Rai & Roberts, 2019). To overcome these challenges, India has advocated for a supportive international framework that facilitates affordable technology access for developing nations (Chaturvedi, 2022). Initiatives like the Green Climate Fund (GCF) aim to address this by funding projects that promote technology transfer and capacity-building in low-income countries (Green Climate Fund, 2021). India has also implemented domestic policies, such as the Perform, Achieve, and Trade (PAT) scheme, to enhance energy efficiency, utilising imported and indigenous technologies to drive sustainability in high-energy sectors (Sharma & Dhar, 2016).

In conclusion, climate finance and technology transfer are instrumental in India's climate strategy, enabling the nation to progress toward its climate goals without compromising economic growth (Dubash & Ghosh, 2021). While India has made strides in securing international collaborations and advocating for equitable finance mechanisms, significant challenges remain in mobilising adequate funds and overcoming barriers to technology access. Enhanced climate finance commitments from developed countries and a supportive framework for technology transfer are essential to strengthening India's climate resilience and supporting its clean energy ambitions (Jørgensen et al., 2021). As India continues to advance its climate policy, the effective integration of climate finance and technology will play a defining role in shaping its low-carbon future.

5. Challenges and Criticisms of India's Climate Commitments

India's climate commitments are driven by the dual objectives of advancing sustainable development and contributing to global climate mitigation. However, balancing the country's ambitious development

agenda with its climate goals presents a significant challenge. As a rapidly developing economy with a vast population, India faces complex trade-offs between fostering economic growth and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. This balancing act and India's advocacy for equitable climate responsibilities have attracted international criticism and praise, sparking debates around the fairness and feasibility of global climate action frameworks.

Balancing Economic Development with Climate Goals

India's primary developmental challenge is addressing poverty, improving infrastructure, and providing universal access to energy and basic amenities for its growing population (Ghosh, 2021). With over 1.4 billion people, a substantial portion of whom live in poverty or lack access to clean energy, India's developmental priorities are closely tied to economic growth and energy consumption (Dubash et al., 2020). The country's energy demand continues to rise as it industrialises and urbanises, making it one of the largest consumers of coal and other fossil fuels (IEA, 2021). While India has made significant strides in renewable energy—such as solar and wind power—its reliance on coal for over 50% of its electricity generation remains a substantial hurdle in meeting stringent climate goals (Bhattacharya & Tongia, 2019).

To balance economic development with climate action, India's approach has often focused on emissions intensity targets (reducing emissions per unit of GDP) rather than absolute emission cuts, allowing for economic growth while aiming to lower the carbon intensity of that growth (Chaturvedi & Shukla, 2016). India's commitments under the Paris Agreement and the Glasgow Climate Pact reflect this approach; it aims to reduce emissions intensity by 45% by 2030 and achieve net-zero emissions by 2070 (UNFCCC, 2021). However, critics argue that these targets fall short of the timelines set by developed countries, highlighting the challenges India faces in scaling down fossil fuel use without hampering its growth (Ghosh, 2022). This balancing act has led India to advocate for climate finance and technology transfer from developed countries to support its low-carbon transition, emphasising that meaningful climate action requires external support for large-scale renewable energy and energy efficiency projects (Jørgensen et al., 2021).

International Criticism and Debates around Equity and Differentiated Responsibilities

India's position on climate equity and "common but differentiated responsibilities" (CBDR) has been central to its climate diplomacy, yet it has faced international criticism, particularly from developed nations, for its stance on emissions reduction timelines (Chaturvedi & Rajamani, 2022). CBDR, a principle rooted in the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), asserts that countries have shared but uneven responsibilities in addressing climate change, considering their historical contributions and development status (UNFCCC, 1992). India argues that developed countries, historically responsible for GHG emissions, should lead mitigation efforts and support developing countries financially and technologically (Dubash et al., 2018).

This stance, however, has faced criticism, as some developed countries contend that all major emitters, including India, should commit to more immediate and ambitious emission reductions to meet global climate targets (Vishwanathan, 2021). For instance, India's commitment to achieve net zero by 2070—two decades beyond the mid-century target of many developed nations—has drawn scrutiny. Critics argue that delaying carbon neutrality threatens the global goal of limiting warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels (IEA, 2021). However, India contends that, with its comparatively low per capita emissions and ongoing development challenges, a 2070 target is realistic and equitable (Ghosh, 2022). Moreover, India emphasises that its climate actions must not compromise poverty reduction and economic development, especially given its vulnerability to climate impacts such as monsoon disruptions, heat waves, and rising sea levels (Singh et al., 2021).

Further debate surrounds India's reliance on climate finance pledges from developed nations, which remain largely unmet. India has repeatedly called attention to the failure of developed countries to mobilise the promised \$100 billion annually in climate finance. This shortfall, India argues, undermines the credibility of international climate frameworks and constrains developing nations' ability to pursue low-carbon growth (Raghavan, 2023). India's position reflects broader concerns within the Global South, where nations argue that equitable climate action should involve fair access to resources and technology (Bhattacharya, 2020).

A delicate balancing act between economic development and climate goals shapes India's climate commitments. Its emphasis on equity and CBDR underscores the need for inclusive climate action, though it faces criticism for its longer timeline and reliance on international support (Jørgensen et al., 2021). While debates around equity and differentiated responsibilities persist, India continues to assert that a just global climate response must account for historical emissions and prioritise development needs. This approach, while controversial, aligns with India's vision of a fair and sustainable future, highlighting the complexities of global climate governance in an era of diverse economic and environmental challenges (Rajamani, 2020).

6. Future Trajectory of India's International Climate Policy

As the climate crisis intensifies, India's role in international climate policy is poised to become increasingly significant, especially as it aligns its sustainable development goals with global climate objectives. India's participation in future climate agreements will likely reflect an expansion of its renewable energy commitments, a stronger focus on adaptation and resilience, and a continued emphasis on equitable climate action through the principle of "common but differentiated responsibilities" (CBDR). India's evolving climate policy trajectory suggests a balance between scaling up its climate commitments and ensuring socio-economic development, making it a critical player in shaping future international climate policies.

Prospects for India's Role in Future Climate Agreements

India's growing influence on the global climate stage positions it as a bridge between developed and developing nations, advocating for equitable climate action that supports sustainable development in the Global South (Chaturvedi, 2022). India will likely advocate for more substantial commitments to climate finance and technology transfer from developed countries to assist developing nations in implementing sustainable growth strategies (Bhattacharya, 2021). India's influence is also anticipated to strengthen within platforms like the G20 and the International Solar Alliance (ISA), where it can further the agenda on green energy, climate adaptation, and resilient infrastructure (International Solar Alliance, 2021).

Regarding emissions reductions, India's 2070 net-zero target and interim goals for 2030 reflect a commitment to gradual decarbonisation (Dubash

& Ghosh, 2022). However, as technology and infrastructure improve, India may advance its climate targets if sufficient financial and technical support is available (Vishwanathan, 2021). India's focus on expanding renewable energy to 500 GW by 2030 underscores its potential to become a leader in clean energy deployment, particularly solar power, which could position India as a model for other developing countries aiming to reduce their carbon footprints without compromising growth (IEA, 2021). Moreover, India's vulnerability to climate impacts will likely increase its advocacy for adaptation and resilience measures within international agreements, pushing for robust financing mechanisms to support communities facing extreme weather events, sea-level rise, and resource scarcity (Ghosh, 2022).

Policy Recommendations and Potential Areas of Improvement

To further enhance its climate policy, India could consider the following policy recommendations:

1. **Increase Climate Ambition through Sector-Specific Targets:** While India's current emissions reduction targets are primarily GDP intensity-based, establishing specific targets for high-emission sectors like transportation, agriculture, and industry could provide more precise pathways to achieving its net-zero goal. Sector-specific targets would also facilitate targeted policy interventions and greater accountability in emission reductions.
2. **Strengthen Adaptation and Resilience Programs:** Given India's high vulnerability to climate impacts, especially in agriculture and coastal areas, increased investment in adaptation measures is essential. India should prioritise building climate-resilient infrastructure, expanding drought and flood management systems, and supporting vulnerable communities. Initiatives like climate-smart agriculture and integrated water resource management could strengthen resilience.
3. **Enhance Domestic Climate Finance Mechanisms:** Although India relies on international climate finance, developing robust domestic financing mechanisms can help reduce this dependency. This could involve incentivising private investment in renewable energy, introducing green bonds, and establishing climate risk insurance

schemes to mobilise resources for sustainable projects. Strengthening domestic finance could enable India to pursue ambitious climate goals independently.

4. **Promote R&D in Clean Technologies:** Investing in research and development for clean energy technologies, carbon capture, and storage can position India as a global leader in climate innovation. Collaborative R&D with international partners and incentives for local tech innovation would support India's energy transition while addressing the barriers of high costs and technology access.
5. **Engage More Actively in Global Climate Diplomacy:** As a representative of the Global South, India's active involvement in climate diplomacy is essential for advocating equitable climate action. India can leverage its G20 leadership and partnerships within the UNFCCC to push for binding commitments on climate finance and technology transfer, ensuring that future agreements are both ambitious and inclusive.
6. **Strengthen Monitoring and Transparency Mechanisms:** India should bolster its climate data collection and monitoring systems to enhance accountability and meet international reporting standards. Improving transparency in emissions tracking, renewable energy deployment, and adaptation progress can enhance India's credibility in international negotiations and ensure it effectively meets its climate goals.

7. Conclusion

India's journey in international climate policy exemplifies a developing nation's pursuit of sustainable growth while balancing global climate commitments. Over the decades, India has shifted from a cautious participant in climate discussions to an assertive advocate for equitable climate action, emphasising "common but differentiated responsibilities" (CBDR) and climate justice. Key agreements like the Paris Agreement and Glasgow Climate Pact highlight India's commitment to integrating its development needs with emissions reduction efforts, positioning it as a significant Global South representative.

India has prioritised renewable energy expansion, emissions intensity reduction, and afforestation, underpinned by substantial investments in solar power, mainly through its leadership in the International Solar

Alliance (ISA). Initiatives such as the National Solar Mission and Perform, Achieve, and Trade (PAT) scheme underscore India's low-carbon transition while ensuring energy access and poverty alleviation. India's 2070 net-zero target and its 2030 goals for reducing GDP emissions intensity and expanding renewable capacity reflect a pragmatic approach to climate action.

However, challenges persist. India's heavy reliance on coal complicates its climate goals, and its emphasis on CBDR has occasionally attracted criticism from developed nations seeking more stringent commitments. In response, India has advocated for fair climate finance and technology transfer, underscoring the need for developed nations' support in achieving sustainable development. As India assumes leadership roles in platforms like the G20, its diplomatic efforts promote green finance and renewable energy across the Global South. Future policy recommendations include sector-specific emissions targets, enhanced domestic climate finance, and collaborative clean technology research. India's climate diplomacy embodies a balanced approach, aligning its national interests with global climate objectives, advancing climate justice, and setting a model for emerging economies as climate challenges intensify.

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